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DEVELOPMENT OF VITAMIN D3-FORTIFIED DAIRY SOUR CREAM DESERT

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Abstract

Recent studies show a correlation between the content of vitamin D3 in the human body and the severity of COVID19. Part of the world's population is deficient in vitamin D3. The solution to this problem is possible by the development and inclusion of foodstuffs fortified with vitamin D in diets. The aim of this study was to develop a D3 -fortified sour cream dessert using an emulsion system as a vitamin D delivery system.

Commercially available raw materials: vitamin D3 powder, sodium carboxymethylcellulose, skimmed milk powder, and sunflower oil were used to create a vitamin D-fortified emulsion. The latter is used in the technology of sour cream dessert production. The emulsion microstructure and stability were investigated using rheology and dynamic light scattering methods. The content of vitamin D3 was determined by coulometric titration and spectroscopy.

Experimentally determined data on the viscosity of emulsions indicate the pseudoplastic behavior of the flow. The use of a structural approach (Casson model) made it possible to determine the emulsion viscosity parameters, which can be used as a quantitative criterion for emulsion stability. This conclusion was confirmed by microstructural data on distribution size of droplets volume of emulsion. Amount of vitamin D in the emulsion and dessert was $1.96 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{g/g}$ (97.8 % of the added amount) and $0.019 \pm 0.005 \mu\text{g/g}$, respectively.

Using the developed stable emulsion as a vitamin D delivery system, a technology for the production of a

dessert based on sour cream fortified with vitamin D3 was proposed.

Key words: Vitamin D, Emulsion Stability, Encapsulation, Fortification, Dairy desert, Skimmed milk powder.

1. Introduction

Optimization of the vitamin status of the population refers to technologies for reducing nutritionally caused and socially significant diseases. This problem is especially aggravated at the present time due to the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic and possible problems in the global food market [1, 2]. The COVID19 pandemic gave a strong impetus to the intensification of research related to the search for ways to increase the immune defense of the human body. Numerous recent studies argue that vitamin D₃ deficiency may be associated with a higher risk of mortality and severe disease in patients with COVID-19 [3]. Patients with vitamin D deficiency were 4.6 times more likely to be positive for COVID-19, and they were 5 times more likely to be infected with COVID-19 than patients with no deficiency [4]. This relationship is most clearly seen in the study of the concentration of 25-hydroxyvitamin-D [25(OH)D] in patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection [5]. The prevalence of VD deficiency in Europe and the Middle East (25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D) in serum < 50 nmol/L or 20 ng/mL) is known [6]. A similar situation is typical for < 20% of the population in Northern Europe, 30 - 60% in Western, Southern and Eastern Europe and up to 80% in the Middle East. Severe deficiency (serum 25(OH)D < 30 nmol/L or 12 ng/mL) is found in

more 10% of Europeans. At the same time, a study [7] notes that elevated levels of D_3 reduce the length of stay of patients in a hospital and facilitate the course of COVID-19. This is because D_3 strengthens the innate immune system and stimulates an adaptive immune response against SARS-CoV-2 infection [8, 9].

It is known that vitamin D_3 can be both synthesized by the human body under the influence of ultraviolet radiation, and enter the body along with food or dietary supplements [10]. However, the modern human diet is characterized by the presence of highly processed foods, usually deficient in vitamin D_3 . This factor, along with insufficient exposure to natural ultraviolet radiation from sunlight, contributes to the development of global D_3 deficiency [10, 11]. Considering this fact, nutraceutical supplementation and vitamin D-rich and vitamin D-fortified foods have a possible mode for ensuring increased consumption and thus improved vitamin D_3 status [12], and in increasing immunity against viral infections such as COVID-19 [13, 14], and research on the technological aspects of food fortification with this vitamin is relevant and timely.

In a previous publication from Gubsky *et al.*, [15], it was noted that the process of introducing vitamin D_3 into food systems is a complex task due to the need to take into account a number of requirements for delivery systems. They must ensure adequate release of bioactive nutrients and their physical and chemical stability under the environmental conditions commonly affecting food and beverages during their manufacture, storage and use. In addition, delivery systems should not adversely affect the physicochemical or organoleptic properties of the food or drink in which they are included, such as appearance, texture or aroma. Compliance with these conditions is achieved when developing food products in the form of emulsions, which are used as effective systems for delivering this vitamin to the human body [16]. When emulsions are used as delivery systems, vitamin D_3 is administered by encapsulation [17 - 19]. This solution is because promising it protects D_3 from factors that lead to its degradation which can easily occur under the influence of external conditions (e.g. high temperature, pH medium, light, atmospheric and mechanical forces) [20]. In addition, the introduction of vitamin D_3 into food systems in the form of emulsions will make it "soluble" in the aquatic environment.

Dairy and sour-milk products, as well as dessert products based on them, are a promising basis for creating dairy and sour-milk products enriched with vitamin D_3 . Moreover, it should be noted that dairy and sour-milk products are in demand among a wide range of consumers. Thus, a large experience of milk

fortification has been accumulated [21]. A study [22] showed a positive relationship between vitamin D-fortified milk consumption and 25(OH)D levels in different population groups. It should be noted that studies [23] have shown that the consumption of vitamin D-fortified dairy products is not a sufficient factor to maintain 25(OH)D at an acceptable level. However, a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials [24] that evaluated the consumption of vitamin D-fortified foods compared with non-fortified foods suggests that fortification of dairy products increased the concentration of 25(OH)D in the body. A study from Sharifi and Jahangiri [25], shows the feasibility and benefits of encapsulation as a nanotechnology in dairy fortification to improve the general health of the population and as a competitive method instead of routine methods to improve the vitamin D_3 status of the population. In addition, research from Leskauskaitė *et al.*, [26], note that vitamin D_3 , which is part of dairy products in an emulsified form, is not destroyed in yogurt or sour cream as a result of processing or storage of these products.

From the point of view of the synergy of the biological activity of individual nutrients, it is of interest to create desserts enriched with vitamin D_3 based on fermented milk products, in particular sour cream. Technologies for enriched dessert products based on fermented milk products, including sour cream, are rather poorly developed. At the same time, sour cream is an excellent and healthy base for desserts. It has a pleasant sour-milk taste, does not have a specific pungent odor, and goes well with other tastes and smells. Sour cream contains useful lactic acid bacteria, contains significant amounts of K, Mg, P, Ca, B vitamins, vitamin C, PP, vitamin E, which makes it a very useful product [27]. Creating a vitamin D-fortified sour cream based dessert will aid calcium absorption. Since, 1,25-hydroxyvitamin D_3 ($1,25(OH)_2D_3$), the hormonally active form of vitamin D_3 , is due to its genomic action the main stimulator of active calcium absorption in the intestine, which includes calcium influx, calcium translocation through the internal part of the enterocyte and basolateral extrusion of calcium by the intestinal plasma membrane pump [28]. Thus, the creation of a technology for the fortification of food products with encapsulated vitamin D_3 , in particular, desserts based on sour cream, is very important. In addition, it should be noted that the natural sour taste of sour cream will allow the additional introduction of ascorbic acid into the dessert based on it, which in food technologies often plays the role of an antioxidant in relation to vegetable oils and certain compounds that are prone to rapid degradation due to oxidation.

The purpose of the research is to study the technological aspects of food fortification with vitamin

D₃ by encapsulating it for subsequent introduction into dessert products, namely the sour cream dessert (SCD).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Reagents and raw materials

We used following reagents and materials:

A. Vitamin D₃ powder (800 IU/g) was purchased from Susin Biotech Co., LTD (Hefei, China). Sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) (reagent purity $\geq 99.5 \pm 3\%$, viscosity of 2% (w/w) solution at 25 °C equals 1,000 - 3,000 mPa x s) was received from Carl Roth GmbH Co (Karlsruhe, Germany). These reagents were food grade.

B. Vitamin D₂ (97% purity) and vitamin D₃ (98% purity) standards, tetra-n-butylammonium bromide, perchloric acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Sodium hydroxide was purchased from Reachim, Russia. Acetonitrile was received from Macron, Germany. All reagents used were analytical grade.

C. Raw materials were purchased from the following suppliers: skimmed milk powder (content, w/w: 1.5% fat, 32.0% protein) from Privet Joint Stock Company Milk Canning Factory, Kupyansk, Ukraine); sunflower oil (TM Oleina refined, deodorized, frozen, content, w/w: 0.05 - 0.06% moisture, no more 12% saturated fat; 14 - 35% monounsaturated fat; 50 - 75% polyunsaturated fat) from Suntrade Subsidiary Enterprise, Ukraine. Sour cream (20% fat), sugar white powder and gelatin instant food (Mriya™, Ukraine) obtained from local stores in city Kharkiv, Ukraine. For preparation of the solutions and emulsions distilled water with electric conductivity less 3 $\mu\text{S}/\text{sm}$ was used.

2.1.2 Preparation of emulsion

The oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions stabilized by proteins of skimmed milk powder and NaCMC were prepared as described by Leskauskaitė *et al.*, [26]. Initially, aqueous solutions of NaCMC (2% w/w) and solutions of skimmed milk powder with a mass protein concentration of 10% w/w for samples were prepared from accurately weighed portions of the corresponding components. All weighing operations were carried out on a balance Ikea (Ikea GmbH, Germany) with accuracy 0.01 g. The non-sheared mixture was stirred and mixed at an appropriate ratio for at least 1 h. The pH and temperature of the mixture was adjusted to 7 using 0.1 N NaOH and was measured by 692 pH/Ion meter (Metrohm, Switzerland) using the combined glass electrode with temperature sensor Pt1000 (Metrohm, Switzerland). The emulsion was made by dispersing the oil phase (sunflower oil) in the necessary protein

and NaCMC mixture for 5 min. at 24,000 rpm using an the IKA Disperser T 25 digital Ultra-Turrax (IKA, Staufen, Germany) homogenizer combined with disperser S25N. The vitamin D₃ solution in ethanol was added to the mixture after 5 minutes after homogenization to prevent vitamin oxidation by air. The final o/w emulsion weighing 100 g contained 40 g sunflower oil, 2 g corresponding protein of SMP, 0.75 g CMC and 2.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ of vitamin D₃. Appearance of the fresh emulsion is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Appearance of fresh vitamin D₃-fortified (w/o) emulsion

2.1.3 Formulations of dairy desert

Sunflower oil and skimmed milk powder are commercially cost-effective and safe ingredients that can become the basic components for the production of o/w emulsions with encapsulated vitamin D. This emulsion was to fortify with vitamin D a sour cream dessert. The basic recipe for the cream was taken from a recipe book [27]. The composition of the ingredients of the formulation is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Formulations of control and vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream dessert

Ingredient, g	Sample	
	Control	Sour cream dessert
Sour cream	690	680
Sugar white powder	178	178
Gelatine	15	15
Water	117	117
Emulsion with vitamin D ₃	-	10*
Total, g	1,000	1,000

Legend: *amount of vitamin D₃ is equivalent to 20 μg , which is 800 IU.

Appearance of the dessert and the view in the section produced according to the formulation (Table 1) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Appearance of vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream dessert

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Rheology

The apparent viscosity of emulsions was determined by using a rotation viscometer Ofite Model 900 viscometer (OFI Testing Equipment, Inc., USA). The device operated with a true Couette coaxial cylinder with combination standard F1.0 spring (constant 386), rotor R1 (radius 1.8414 cm) and bob B1 (radius 1.7245 cm, height 3.8 cm) in variable speed range 1 - 1,000 rpm with speed accuracy 0.001 rpm. All measurements were carried out at shear rate constant 1.7023 s/RPM, overall instrument constant 300 and maximum shear stress 0.0168 mN/cm². Calibration Fluid Batch: 100 cP Nist N 132-80 (OFI Testing Equipment, Inc., USA) was used to calibrate of viscometer at a temperature of 298 K. The procedure for calibrating the viscometer, measurements, and calculation of the effective dynamic viscosity were performed as in [29]. In experiments to obtain a flow curve close to the equilibrium state, sequential measurements were carried out (↑↓↑), where ↑ means viscosity measuring with increasing shear rate, and ↓ conversely.

2.2.2 Dynamic light scattering

The particle size distributions of the emulsions were measured using a particle and molecular size analyzer (Zetasizer Nano ZS, Malvern Instruments Ltd., Melvin, UK) with dynamic light scattering (DSL) technology and backscatter detector (scattering angle 173°). The procedure for measurements and calculation of this values were performed as in Gubsky *et al.*, [15]. The samples were diluted with double distilled water until a diluted solution viscosity of 2 mPa x s was reached (approximately diluted 100-fold v/v). The particle size measurements are reported as the average and standard deviation of measurements made on two freshly prepared samples, with two readings made per sample. All calculations using experimental data and graphical representation of the results were carried out in the Zetasizer software v.8.02 (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Melvin, UK).

2.2.3 Visual creaming stability

The creaming stability of emulsions was assessed visually from the height of the serum phase developing with storage of emulsion samples in a cylindrical glass tube (20 × 60 mm). Creaming index (CI) of emulsion were measured as in [30]. An amount of 25 mL of samples was placed in a tube and stored at 25 °C for stored for: 1, 4, 7 days after the preparation. With the passage of time, the interface between the two phases was analyzed: the first phase was rich in oil, and the second phase, which was turbid and more abundant in the lower part of the tube. Creaming index of emulsion as the percent ratio of the height of cream layer HC (mm) and to the height of total emulsion HT (mm) were calculated by expression (2):

$$CI (\%) = \frac{HC}{HT} 100 \quad (2)$$

2.2.4 Vitamin D analysis

The amount of vitamin D₃ in ethanol solutions added to the emulsion was determined by the galvanostatic coulometry with electrogenerated bromine as in Gubsky *et al.*, [31] with modification from Mazur *et al.*, [32]. The electrogeneration of bromine was performed using a 0.2 M (C₂H₅)₄NBr and 0.1 M HClO₄ in acetonitrile [33]. Vitamin D₃ in emulsion and sample was determined using a validated method involving high-performance liquid chromatography with UV spectroscopic detection and vitamin D₂ as an internal standard according Phillips *et al.*, [34]. Sample preparation was performed with slight modifications as in Patterson *et al.*, [35], using AOAC method 992.26 [36]. The samples were purified and concentrated by normal-phase HPLC with a Zorbax SIL column (250 mm × 9.4 mm, 5µm; no. 880952-201, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) and the mobile phase consisted of 99.5% n-hexane and 0.5% alcohols (ration 2:1(v/v) 2-propanol to methanol). The final purification was achieved using a Zorbax ODS QC column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5µm; no. 880952-702, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) with a mobile phase of acetonitrile/methylene chloride (65/35, v/v).

2.2.5 Sensory analysis

An preliminary acceptance test was used to evaluate the following attributes in the samples: color and appearance, odor, consistency, shape, taste, aftertaste and general impression by the ISO's methods [37, 38]. The sensory analysis was performed on the laboratory of sensory analysis at State Biotechnological University (Kharkiv, Ukraine). The panelists stayed in the room with temperature 25 ± 2 °C and the relative humidity 55 ± 3%. The samples were prepared 1 h before the evaluation. Samples were kept in coded plates covered with aluminum foil. Ten trained panelists were selected

to guarantee the evaluation accuracy. The intensity of each sensory characteristic was recorded on a 5-point hedonic scale after 1 h orientation sessions. In this session the panelists had specified the terminology and anchor points on the scale. The coded samples were shown simultaneously and evaluated in random order.

2.2.6 Statistical analysis

For the statistical analysis were used a one-factor analysis (ANOVA) for a series of parallel measurements at least 3. Value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The Tukey-Kramer honestly significant test was used to determine significant difference between means. All data were expressed as average value \pm standard deviation. Basic statistic and ANOVA were performed using the statistical software package Minitab ver. 18.1 (Minitab Inc., USA).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Stability of emulsion

The most promising approach to protect vitamin D from degradation in a food matrix is its introduction into an emulsion by encapsulation [39]. However, according to classical concepts [40], an emulsion in the macro- and nanoranges is a thermodynamically unstable system prone to destabilization and stratification with time.

Therefore, the stability and structural properties of emulsions should be considered as a necessary condition for the development of the technology of one or another emulsion-based food. In this study, the stability of the emulsion significantly affects the preservation of vitamin D₃ during storage. Several properties can be used as indicators of the stability of emulsions during storage. The creaming stability, rheological properties and distribution size of droplets of the emulsions were used as indicators of the stability of emulsions during storage [41]. The instability of the system is usually associated with the thermodynamic instability of the system and the desire to reduce the free energy by aggregating the particles of the system. It is known that the aggregation of particles affects the shelf life and organoleptic properties [42], while the rheological properties determine the texture [43].

3.1.1 Physical stability

According to McClements [44], the creaming index characterizes the gravitational separation in emulsions. The lower the CI value, the more stable the emulsion. In this study, the emulsions were stored at 4 °C for 7 days to evaluate their physical stability over time (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Creaming index of the vitamin D₃-fortified emulsion during storage

Aggregation of oil droplets, including flocculation and coalescence, occurs over time and leads to the formation of a creamy layer in emulsions [40]. This result is consistent with numerous previous studies that reported a higher level of emulsion break index with increasing shelf life [26, 30, and 45]. The creaming stability measurements showed that emulsions were stable after 7 days of storage. The resulting change in CI is only 1.2% over the time period studied. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the developed technology of the final product implies a significantly shorter shelf life.

3.1.2 Rheological characterization of emulsion

Most food emulsions are non-Newtonian fluids exhibiting thixotropic behavior. Thixotropy is an inherent property of a structured disperse system in which particles of the dispersed phase form aggregates, most often flocculants. However, weak or reversible flocculation allows the destruction and re-formation of aggregates with the achievement of a metastable thermodynamic state. Approximately this state is achieved using the measurement technique given in section 2.2.1. The apparent viscosity values determined in this way are discussed further.

On Figure 4 shows the dependence of shear stress on shear strain rate for fresh emulsion and after 7 days of storage. The flow curves have a non-linear dependence shear stress versus shear rate. Such behavior is characteristic of the non-Newtonian type of flow.

Figure 4. Curve of flow of vitamin D₃-fortified (w/o) emulsion

Steady shear flow curves are usually well described by the power law model (3):

$$\tau = K\gamma^n \quad (3)$$

Where: coefficient K is the consistency index and n the power law index.

The experimental data on the dependence shear stress on shear rate are adequately approximated by equation (3) with a determination coefficient of 0.9998 for FE and 0.9961 for E7. As a result of the calculations, consistency coefficients of 11.68 ± 0.18 and 22.95 ± 0.85 , and flow coefficients of 0.416 ± 0.003 and 0.373 ± 0.009 were obtained for fresh emulsion and emulsion after 7 days of storage, respectively. Flow index values less than 0 indicate typical pseudoplastic flow. An increase in K and a decrease in n in the series of emulsions testifies in favor of an increase in the structuredness of the resulting emulsions. The reason for this may be the aggregation of droplets into flocules.

The disadvantage of this model is the fact that both coefficients are physically unfounded. Therefore, earlier in studies from Gubsky *et al.*, [15, 29], explanations of the obtained rheological data in food systems were carried out within the framework of the structural approach using the generalized flow equation of the Casson rheological model [46]. The rheological behavior of food dispersed systems within the framework of the model under discussion is explained by a change in the structure. This model was developed for describing dispersed systems, including emulsions and suspensions [47, 48]. In applicability to emulsions, the latter is understood as a certain arrangement in space of individual or interconnected particles. In our case, emulsion drops. The structure is characterized by the size distribution of particle aggregates, the shape of particles or aggregates, the internal structure of

the aggregates, and their orientation in space. Such a representation is a generalization and extension to real systems of the classical Casson microrheological model [49] with an additional interpretation of the coefficients of this model based on the kinetic equations of destruction - the restoration of structural aggregates of the Cross model [50]. The proposed mechanism of viscous flow is associated with the dissipation of the energy of this flow when flowing around a set of aggregates and individual particles under the condition of their hydrodynamic interaction, the possible destruction of aggregates due to tearing hydrodynamic forces, and the combination during collisions of aggregates. This model can be applied to consider the behavior of emulsions in time, and the process of changing the size of aggregates can be due to the instability of the system and the aggregation of emulsion droplets, in particular, due to flocculation. Thus, the quantitative parameters calculated using this theory can be considered as indicators of system instability associated with the phenomena of creaming and sedimentation.

Figure 5 shows the dependence of viscosity on shear rate for the fresh emulsions and emulsion after 7 days of storage.

Figure 5. Curve of apparent viscosity curves on shear stress in double logarithmic coordinates

The resulting curves in double logarithmic coordinates have an approximate linear dependence, demonstrating typical shear-thinning behavior. This behavior is typical for the area of dilution of emulsions [51]. After 7 days of storage, the viscosity of the emulsion increases.

For disperse systems with pseudoplastic behavior at low shear rates, an indestructible structure is characteristic as a result of the interaction of particles and the effects

of Brownian motion. This structure is characterized by a constant value of viscosity η_0 , called the zero-shear viscosity, and a zero-shear viscosity plateau is observed on the viscosity versus shear rate curve. It is this value that can be used as an indicator of structural changes in the emulsion over time. To calculate it, the generalized flow equation of the Casson rheological model should be used for the apparent viscosity of emulsion in the form of an expression (4):

$$\eta^{1/2} = \frac{\tau_c^{1/2}}{\chi + \gamma^{1/2}} + \eta_c^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Where: the coefficient τ_c is the degree of aggregation of the system and takes on the meaning of the limiting dynamic shear stress only under the condition; the coefficient χ is associated with the looseness or compactness of an individual aggregate of particles, and it determines the plastic or pseudoplastic behavior of a structured system; the coefficient η_c is Casson viscosity equal to the viscosity of the system with complete destruction of the original aggregates.

Within the framework of this approach, it is possible to calculate values η_0 and η_∞ are viscosities of emulsion at the shear rate approaches zero and $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, respectively:

$$\eta_0^{1/2} = \frac{\tau_c^{1/2}}{\chi} + \eta_c^{1/2} \text{ at } \gamma \rightarrow 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_\infty^{1/2} \cong \eta_c^{1/2} \text{ at } \gamma \rightarrow \infty \quad (6)$$

The values determined by the approximation of experimental data according to equation (4) values $\tau_c^{1/2}$, χ and $\eta_c^{1/2}$ were used to calculate the values η_0 and η_∞ according to equations (6) and (7). The results obtained are given in Table 2.

It has been known that decreasing the droplet size of emulsions increases the viscosity [44]. This is due to the denser packing of the emulsion structure. In this case, one should speak about the formation of droplet aggregates. This process increases the viscosity of the emulsion, which is associated with the movement of larger particles and an increase in the hydrodynamic resistance of the medium to this movement. As can be seen from Table 3, the value of τ_c for the E7 emulsion is greater than for FE. This indicates an increase in the degree of aggregation of the droplet. The calculations

performed allow us to consider the coefficient τ_c as an indicator of changes in the microstructure of the emulsion and, thus, an indicator of its stability. Unlike the consistency coefficient, which is widely used in the interpretation of rheological data as an adjustable parameter and has no physical meaning, the coefficient τ_c is introduced on the basis of the kinetic model of destruction-recovery of the structural aggregates of the system [47]. This fact should be considered as a significant advantage of its use to characterize the stability of emulsion systems.

Table 2 shows the fact of the increase in the value of zero-shear viscosity during storage of the emulsion. According to equation (5), this value integrates all the effects associated with the flow of the emulsion. The first term of Eq. (5) corresponds to energy dissipation during the flow around aggregates of macromolecules, and the second term corresponds to energy losses during the motion of individual macromolecules. From which follows the possibility of considering the parameter η_∞ as the total viscosity of the system with complete destruction of polymer associates. A slight increase in this parameter can be interpreted as a change in droplet size due to coalescence. The coefficients τ_c and χ characterize the degree of aggregation of the system and the degree of looseness or compactness of aggregates (or associates of macromolecules) in polymer solutions, respectively [48]. These coefficients are related to the parameters of the kinetic equation, which considers the motion of particles in a viscous medium, aggregating during mutual collision, and separating under the influence of thermal motion and hydrodynamic tensile forces. Despite the fact that the value of η_0 includes the value of η_∞ , its change in the increase during storage of the emulsion is greater compared to the change in η_∞ . This fact testifies in favor of the assumption about the predominance of the flocculation process in the process of droplet aggregation, i.e. the formation of larger aggregates without changing the droplet size. Thus, the calculation within the framework of the structural model of the emulsion of the value of zero-shear viscosity is the best methods for monitoring the physical stability of emulsions due to the aggregation of its drops. It should be noted that this approach is not new and was used for a similar purpose earlier [52–54], but with a different methodology.

Table 2. Coefficients the generalized flow equation of the Casson rheological model and calculated value of zero-shear viscosity and viscosity of the emulsion with complete destruction of structure

Day of storage	$\tau_{\bar{n}}^{1/2}$	χ	$\eta_{\bar{n}}^{1/2}$	R^2	$\eta_0, \text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$	$\eta_\infty, \text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$
0	6.0 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	0.34 ± 0.01	0.9996	36.6	116
7	8.8 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.1	0.35 ± 0.03	0.9979	57.7	123

3.1.3 Distribution size of droplets

An indication of droplet aggregation in the emulsions was obtained from measurement of the size of the oil droplets. The droplet size is an important factor in emulsion and its stability. The droplets of a certain size formed are the result of the dispersion of the oil into small drops, followed by the adsorption of surface-active emulsifier molecules on them. The system thus obtained is thermodynamically unstable, but with a relative kinetic resistance to sedimentation and creaming [55]. Kinetic stability is affected by two opposite processes. Thus, the interaction of droplets with forces of different nature leads to their aggregation [56]. Important and dominant in this process is flocculation, i.e. the formation of large droplets due to the coalescence of smaller droplets. On the other hand, the solvation of droplets by molecules of the continuous phase helps prevent droplet coalescence due to electrostatic or steric effects [57]. It is obvious that the size of oil droplets is an essential characteristic in assessing the stability of an emulsion over time.

The size distribution of oil droplets by volume in fresh emulsion and in emulsion after 7 days of storage is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Distribution size of droplets volume of fresh emulsion (solid line with box) and of emulsion after 7 days of storage (short dash line with dot)

These distributions are bimodal and characterize the process of small aggregation of emulsion droplets in both samples. As can be seen, the initial emulsion has a pronounced mode with a maximum of 1.6 and 5.3 μm (Table 3).

This distribution is typical for individual drops. This distribution covers about 95% of the droplets by volume. The second and fairly wide distribution has a weakly pronounced maximum at about 5 μm and is associated with the droplet aggregates formed as a result of flocculation. This bimodal droplet distribution is characterized by a polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.308 and a Z-average diameter of 1.9 μm . As a result of storing the emulsion for 7 days, its stability changes slightly, as evidenced, as shown above, by a decrease in the creaming index (Table 2) and an increase in the value of η_0 (Table 3). In this case, there is a shift in the maximum of the distribution curve of droplets in the direction of increasing their size with a simultaneous decrease in their number from 95% to 83%. At the same time, the number of floccules formed as a result of the interaction of droplets increases, and this mode is characterized by a wider size distribution compared to the initial one for a fresh emulsion. These changes lead to an increase in the polydispersity index to 0.454 and the average droplet diameter to 2.1 μm .

Smaller droplets can lead to greater resistance to coalescing and flocculation due to reduced Brownian motion and gravitational forces [55]. The polydispersity index, which characterizes the size distribution of droplets, is related to the stability of the emulsion. Low PDI values represent a narrower particle size distribution, hence a small difference in droplet size. In general, emulsions with narrower PDI values are more stable than emulsions with a wider PDI value. The results obtained indicate a change in particle size, probably, the formation of larger floccules from single droplets due to their aggregation, which increases with increasing storage time of the emulsion. This is reflected in an increase in the polydispersity index from 0.308 to 0.454 and, accordingly, leads to a decrease in the stability of the emulsion. This is confirmed by the increase in CI (Figure 3). These conclusions agree very well with the rheological data. The values of coefficient τ_c as the degree of aggregation of the system calculated above also increased with an increase in the storage period by 46.7%. The resulting increase in PDI of 47.4% is in very good agreement with this value. Similar behavior was obtained for the zero-shear viscosity of the emulsion calculated using the structural approach on the Casson model. This integral value includes all three parameters of this microrheological model and

Table 3. Size distribution of droplets by volume after preparation and after 7 days of storage of emulsions at temperature 4 °C

Storage, day	Z-average diameter d, μm	Polydispersity index	Peaks (mean)			
			Drops peak		Flocs peak	
			Diameter, μm	Percentage of total	Diameter, μm	Percentage of total
0	1.9	0.308	1.6 \pm 0.4	95	5.3 \pm 0.3	5
7	2.1	0.454	2.2 \pm 0.8	83	4.9 \pm 0.6	17

can therefore be used in the future as a criterion for the droplets aggregation of emulsion. Based on this study, this criterion should still be considered more as a qualitative characteristic of changes in the structure and stability of the system. Quantitative correlations require additional accumulation of experimental material with emulsions of different nature.

3.2 Stability of vitamin D₃ in emulsion

The emulsion stability results obtained in the previous section are an important factor in the development of a commercial vitamin D fortified food product. In a study from Leskauskaitė *et al.*, [26], it was noted that due to the instability of emulsions and possible separation, conditions may arise that lead to the degradation of vitamin D. Despite the positive results regarding the stability of the emulsion, the issue of determining the content of vitamin D in the emulsion is still important.

Studies of the stability of vitamin D in the emulsion consisted of two stages. At the first stage, it was necessary to investigate the preservation of vitamin D during the preparation of the emulsion and determine its content in the freshly prepared emulsion. A preliminary experiment showed that the enrichment of the emulsion with vitamin D in an amount of more than 2 µg/g of emulsion makes it possible to obtain a 95% preservation of vitamin D in the prepared emulsion. The introduction of a smaller amount leads to unsatisfactory results, indicating a significantly lower content of the vitamin to the level of 60% of the entered. The results obtained are in good agreement with the data from Leskauskaitė *et al.*, [26], for emulsions with rapeseed oil as the fat phase. Considering the above facts 2 µg/g-fortified emulsion. Analyzing data of freshly prepared emulsions, it was determined that an average recovery of the vitamin from this emulsion was 1.96 ± 0.22 or 97.8 % from the initial amount added.

At the second stage, an experiment was carried out to study the safety of vitamin during storage in the dark at 4 °C. Figure 7 shows the content of vitamin D₃ in emulsions.

Figure 7. Vitamin D₃ content in emulsions during storage at 4 °C in the dark.
Standard deviation shown as error bars

As can be seen from the Figure 7, the vitamin D₃ content in the emulsions did not change during storage. After 7 days in storage at 4 °C in the dark, the content of vitamin D in emulsions enriched with 2 µg/g of vitamin D₃ was only 0.04 µg/g less. That is, the decrease of vitamin D was 1.6 %.

3.3 Development of vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream technology

There is a lack of information in the literature about the experience of enriching desserts based on dairy products, including sour cream, with vitamins of the lipophilic group. Although from the point of view of technology development such products are a promising basis for fortification with fat-soluble vitamins:

- Such products are not subject to significant heat treatment;
- They have a fairly short shelf life, which guarantees the stability of the content of vitamin D₃;
- They allow the introduction of vitamin D in both encapsulated and non-encapsulated form.

When fortifying food, a very important issue is to calculate the optimal amount of vitamin D in the emulsion itself and in the finished product. Levels of enrichment of food products for mass consumption should be harmonized with European and domestic regulations and are not less than 15 and not more than 50% of the physiological needs of the average daily dose (100 g, or 100 mL, or 100 kcal for foods with high energy value) or in one package of the product (if it contains one portion) [56].

Based on this, oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions encapsulated with vitamin D₃ stabilized with milk powder and carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) were prepared in such a way that the final emulsion contained 80 IU of cholecalciferol per gram of emulsion. Given all the above, it was decided that it is advisable to apply the emulsion with encapsulated vitamin D₃ at the stage of whipping sour cream after cooling to further prepare the dessert "Sour cream". Based on the recommendations from Kodentsova [56], and taking into account the requirements of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine [57], the daily requirement of an adult in vitamin D₃ is 5 µg, which corresponds to 200 IU, it was noted that it would be rational to apply an emulsion of encapsulated vitamin D₃ 100 g of product. This will be 80 IU of cholecalciferol in one serving of dessert.

The stage of the technological process of making a dessert for the introduction of an emulsion with encapsulated vitamin D must meet the following requirements: the environment in which the emulsion is applied must not have a high temperature; after the introduction of vitamin D, the use of heat treatment

is impractical, as it will lead to some degradation of vitamin D. Given the above requirements, the flow chart of the vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream dessert manufacturing process is shown in the Figure 8.

Figure 8. Flow chart of the vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream dessert manufacturing process

The given flow chart of the vitamin D₃-fortified sour cream dessert manufacturing process involves the preliminary preparation of three intermediate stages of creating semi-finished products from the original ingredients. The first of them is primarily the production of an emulsion enriched with vitamin D. The second involves the creation of a whipped semi-finished product based on sour cream and sugar. For this, sour cream pre-cooled to 10 - 15 °C is whipped for 7 min. using a mixer (11000 PRM) with the gradual addition of powdered sugar. The third stage of preliminary preparation is necessary for the production of an aqueous solution of gelatin by dissolving it at a temperature of 45 °C. The emulsion obtained in the above way (o/w) is mixed with sour cream whipped with sugar and the resulting mixture is whipped with a mixer for 4 min. At the end of whipping, a warm gelatin solution is slowly added to the mixture whipped in this way. The resulting mixture is placed in molds for solidification, followed by cooling in refrigerator during 150 min. at temperature 4 °C.

The technology of sour cream dessert with vitamin D₃ differs from the traditional one in that before the stage of adding a gelatin solution, an emulsion with

vitamin D₃ is added to the recipe mixture. Thus, the total whipping time remains the same, however, at the seventh minute of whipping, an emulsion with vitamin D₃ is added, and about a minute before the end of whipping, a gelatin solution is introduced. The subsequent stages are carried out according to the technology described in [27]. The stage of introducing an emulsion with vitamin D₃ in the proposed technology of sour cream dessert enriched with vitamin D₃ meets the following requirements: minimization of interaction with atmospheric oxygen during whipping (the emulsion is introduced only 7 minutes after the start of whipping), uniform distribution of the emulsion throughout the volume of the product.

As in the case of the emulsion, a study was conducted on the stability of vitamin D in the developed dessert. The initial content of vitamin D₃ in the sour cream was $0.019 \pm 0.005 \mu\text{g/g}$. The vitamin D content after 7 days in storage at 4 °C in the dark decreased of 0.8%. The result obtained should be considered satisfactory, taking into account the fact that for this product, according to the technical specifications, the shelf life is 2 times less.

3.4 Sensory analysis

The information obtained during the sensory evaluation of the characteristics of the product has a strong influence on consumer choice. In addition, sensory characteristics are an important tool for technologists-developers, as they help in achieving certain indicators of quality and safety of the target product. The results of the evaluation of sensory characteristics (color and appearance, smell, consistency, shape, taste, aftertaste, general impression) are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of the evaluation of sensory characteristics

Characteristic	Control	Sour cream dessert
Color and appearance	4.81 ± 0.46	4.81 ± 0.46
Odor	4.85 ± 0.23	4.85 ± 0.23
Consistency	4.74 ± 0.44	4.74 ± 0.44
Shape	4.74 ± 0.44	4.74 ± 0.44
Taste	4.85 ± 0.23	4.85 ± 0.23
Aftertaste	4.85 ± 0.23	4.56 ± 0.56
General impression	4.61 ± 0.54	4.61 ± 0.54

Two-samples T-tests were used to test whether the mean values of the sensory scores of the control sample and the dessert differ significantly, those to assess the effect of added vitamin D. The results of calculating the average values of sensory indicators and their comparison shows that means for these samples are not significantly different (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Biplot of two-samples T-test of the mean values of the sensory scores of the control and SCD samples

In general, the Control and SCD samples received the same scores for all sensory characteristics, except for the aftertaste indicator. This indicator is higher in the control sample, since the experts noted a very weak (at the disappearance level) aftertaste of sunflower oil in the vitamin D₃-fortified dairy sour cream dessert sample.

4. Conclusions

- The results of this study show that an emulsion stabilized with a protein complex (contained in milk powder) as an emulsifier and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose as a medium thickener remains stable over time. Such a conclusion can be drawn from the data of the creaming index study. The change in this parameter after 7 days of storage of the emulsion at 4 °C in the dark was only 1.2%, which should be considered as a satisfactory result. This suggests that such an emulsion is a suitable system for delivering vitamin D₃ to the human body in the production of vitamin D₃-fortified dairy products. The stability of the emulsion was also investigated by rheology and dynamic light scattering methods. To interpret the rheological data, two models were used: a power law and a microrheological model of an emulsion as a structured system. Calculated within both models, the consistency coefficient for the power-law model and the coefficient τ_c as the degree of aggregation of the system for the structural approach indicate the process of aggregation of emulsion drops in time. Apparently, this is due to the process of flocculation of emulsion droplets into larger aggregates.

- In the emulsion used for fortification with vitamin D and the dessert produced on its basis, a satisfactory preservation of encapsulated vitamin D is observed. Thus, the analysis for a fresh emulsion average recovery of the vitamin was $97.8 \pm 1.1\%$. At the same time, after 7 days in storage at 4 °C in the dark, only 1.6% loss of vitamin D is observed. Similar results were obtained for the developed dessert. At the initial content of vitamin D₃ in the sour cream was $0.019 \pm 0.005 \mu\text{g/g}$, after 7 days in storage at 4 °C in the dark its content of 0.8%

decreased.

- The developed technology for fortifying a dairy product with vitamin D involves the use of natural, widely used and familiar ingredients, such as sunflower oil, sour cream and powdered milk, which is positive for expanding the range of dairy products on the market and their adequate perception by the consumer. The proposed recipe composition of dessert with vitamin D, taking into account the recommended dosage of vitamin for enrichment from 15 to 50% of the daily requirement. The preservation of the latter in the final product is achieved due to its encapsulation in the fat phase and the reception of the introduction at the last stage of whipping the mixture for the preparation of the dessert. According to sensory analysis, vitamin D-fortified dairy dessert differs from the control sample produced by traditional technology.

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